

Table 1. Grain yield of ADT42 in Tamil Nadu, India. 1986-93.

Trial and year	Locations (no.)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		Increase over check (%)
		ADT42	IR50 (check)	
TNRRRI, Aduthurai, 1986-93	8	6.0	4.5	33
Multilocation trials at research stations, 1990-92	22	5.5	4.8	15
Adaptive research trials in farmers' fields, 1992	61	5.5	5.2	7
Total/weighted mean	91	5.7	4.8	10

Table 2. Reaction of ADT42 to blast and BPH in Tamil Nadu, India. 1990-92.

Disease/insect	Mean score ^a	
	ADT42	IR50 (check)
Blast	3.4	8.7
BPH	3.7	7.0

^aScored under artificial conditions using the scoring methods in *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

CORH1: the first rice hybrid for Tamil Nadu, India

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CORH1 is a rice hybrid selected at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, from hybrids shared by IRRI through DRR, Hyderabad. The hybrid is developed using the cytoplasmic genetic male sterility and fertility restorer system. IR62829 A and IR10198-66-2 R are the parents.

CORH1 matures in 100-115 d and is up to 75 cm tall. It has high-tillering ability, giving up to 20 productive tillers/hill at 25- x 20-cm spacing. The average grain number is 150/panicle; its 1,000-grain weight is 20 g. Grains are medium slender and straw-colored; kernels are

Yield of CORH1 (t/ha) compared with IR50 and Rasi, Tamil Nadu, India.

Type of trial	Year	Trials (no.)	CORH1 ^a	IR50	Rasi
Research station	1990-92	4	5.2	4.6	-
Multilocation	1991 kharif	7	5.7	4.4	-
Multilocation	1992 kharif	6	5.2	4.8	-
Multilocation	1993 kharif	3	5.4	4.3	-
Large-scale demonstration	1993 kharif	4	5.2	4.9	-
On-farm	1992 kharif	14	6.1	5.2	-
On-farm	1993 kharif	18	6.3	5.4	-
National hybrid rice	1990-91	18	6.2	-	5.1
Mean		74	5.9	5.0	5.1

^a% over IR50 = 118.8; Rasi = 117.3.

white. CORH1 is best suited for May-Jun sowing in Tamil Nadu.

The mean grain yield for CORH1 at 74 locations in research station, on-farm, and national hybrid rice trials (see table) was 5.9 t/ha compared with 5.0 t/ha for IR50. The mean biological yield of CORH1 was 11.2 t/ha (5.9 t grain and 5.3 t straw). The highest recorded grain yield was 10.1 t/ha (see figure).

Physical, cooking, chemical, and organoleptic characters are all good. CORH1 is moderately resistant to whitebacked planthopper, brown

planthopper, green leafhopper, sheath rot, brown spot, and rice tungro virus under field conditions.

The Tamil Nadu State Variety Release Committee approved the release of CORH1 in Dec 93 and the state government released it for general cultivation during kharif season (Jun-Sep) 1994. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Average and highest yield of CORH1, Tamil Nadu, India.